

Hypothetical Axiom of “Complete Symmetry” and a New Concept of Spacetime

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Abstract

The hypothetical principle of “Complete Symmetry” is introduced as a candidate for a novel physical axiom. To be compatible with it, spacetime must be emergent. In the suggested model, the state of spacetime at a specific point in time and space is a superposition of future states, but also of past states and states of spatial distance. It depends on the observers pure “here and now state”. The traditional well-defined energy distribution in Minkowski space becomes a probabilistic superposition, which is only sharp at the observer. In this static view, time does not progress in a traditional sense. However, it features a direction. Remarkably, the observed duality of waves and particles arises automatically and is not an independent physical phenomenon.

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1 Introduction

Physicists tend to prefer theories describing distinct physical phenomena by means of symmetries instead of requiring several independent principles. Although supersymmetry is a hypothetical concept to extend the Standard Model, its properties are investigated using quantum mechanical model systems [1]. Interestingly the demand for symmetries is treated rather inconsistently in different areas of physics. For example, the Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics is traditionally preferred [2] over the more symmetric Many Worlds interpretation. This inconsistency of dealing with symmetries motivates further investigation. A basic goal of this work is to overcome this arbitrariness by pursuing the uncompromised approach of examining the hypothetical axiom of “Complete Symmetry”.

The ongoing search of a coherent description of nature is complicated by the incompatibility between General Relativity and the Standard Model [3]. A better understanding of relativistic quantum effects is not only of an epistemological nature, but is also required for highly sensitive gravity measurement technologies [4]. Semi-classical quantum field theories in curved spacetime (QFTCS) are based on Minkowski space to take relativistic effects into account. Unfortunately, the expectation, laws of physics have to describe transitions from an initial to a final state as a temporal process, decreases the attention for theories where spacetime is not the “fundamental stage”. The axiom of “Complete Symmetry” requires spacetime to be emergent. In addition to the axiom itself, this work presents an example of a conceptual model of spacetime that might be compliant with it.

2 Hypothetical Axiom of “Complete Symmetry”

2.1 Definition

“There is a completely symmetric fundamental representation of reality without any randomness implied.”

2.2 Clarifying Statements

The designation “reality” in particular includes the observable universe and its laws of physics, but is not limited thereupon. It also comprises all objects, the laws of nature and abstract concepts declared by the hypothetical fundamental description.

The phrase “completely symmetric” postulates, that there exists a way to describe reality in an absolutely symmetric manner. If there exist different symmetric, fundamentally realizable

variants, all variants must be realized. This requirement has to be applied to any fundamental concept, such as parameters, fundamental rules or observational results.

For instance, any fundamental theory complying to the axiom and requiring a physical constant has to explain in a logically consistent way (as for example in case of the 248 dimensions of the exceptionally symmetrical E8), why exactly the specific value is to be expected. From this point of view symmetry and absence of randomness are closely interconnected.

Based on the above considerations, the phrase “completely symmetric” alone already implies that there must not be any randomness implied in a fundamental description. However, for the sake of clarity, the absence of randomness is also explicitly mentioned.

2.3 Opposing Observations

At first glance this axiom seems simply invalid, contradicted by countless opposing observations perceptible in daily life. Without claim to completeness, the most impactful observations can essentially be divided into the following categories:

Spacetime has exactly three spatial dimensions and one temporal dimension, though from a mathematical point of view, Minkowski spaces come along in various dimensions with different metric signatures. Time contains a further asymmetry in itself, represented by its temporal direction from past to future.

Laws of nature: Seemingly arbitrary group composition $SU(3) \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)$ of the Standard Model, only left-handed neutrinos, inexplicable natural constants, ...

Mainly relevant in Copenhagen Interpretation: Inhomogeneous distribution of energy and matter within space

Only relevant in Copenhagen Interpretation: The laws of nature lead to random results.

In addition to defining the axiom, the present article focusses on point 1 of the above list by suggesting a concept of reality and spacetime, which is supposed to facilitate the modeling of an emergent spacetime from a completely symmetric concept. The axiom mandatorily requires an interpretation with “Many Worlds”. The “Copenhagen Interpretation” (random results of measurements) as well as the “Pilot Wave Interpretation” [5] (arbitrary hidden variables) cannot act as fundamental representations. Thus, point 4 does not require further investigation and point 3 does not directly falsify the axiom. A follow-up article will suggest ideas, how point 2 and 3 could possibly be dealt with. However, no completely symmetric unified description will be defined there either, leaving plenty of scope for further research.

Remarkably, if the axiom will be proven to be false, this would lead to a gain of knowledge, too. In this case, every fundamental description of reality would have to feature at least one break of symmetry and the preferred variant would define a fundamental random parameter of nature. Thus, every imaginable candidate for an upcoming unifying theory would exhibit the insufficiency of not being able to give a cogent reason for this parameter. From this perspective, the negation of the axiom seems even more implausible than the axiom itself. This insight additionally justifies further examination of the axiom.

2.4 Assumption about Nature's Laws

A widespread assumption among physicists is, that the laws of physics necessarily have to describe the transition from an “initial configuration” (e. g. of particles with a spatial distribution) into a “final configuration”. Because of this focus on spatiotemporal processes, spacetime is expected to act as a kind of a fundamental “stage” [6], where particles “perform actions” in compliance with the laws of physics.

2.5 Necessary Adjustments

Assuming the axiom to be true, either a proof of necessity of the observed dimensions of spacetime has to be provided (for example by a completely symmetric quantum theory of emerging spacetime), or spacetime consequently must be ruled out as the fundamental space. The same holds true for the Standard Model. Consequently, spacetime, the Standard Model and gravity have to be emergent from a completely symmetric, yet unknown underlying mechanism. This paper will take a first step and suggest, how the current concept of spacetime could be readjusted to be more suited therefore. In that sense, the presented model of spacetime was inspired by the axiom. However, it is emphasized, that neither the axiom is a necessary condition for the new model of spacetime nor vice versa.

3 New Model of Spacetime

General Relativity provides the concept of an unambiguous energy and matter distribution mutually interacting with a clearly defined spacetime. Within an inertial system, the distribution of matter as a function of temporal and spatial position is well defined. The following thought experiments will examine the limits of this concept by taking quantum effects into account.

3.1 Traditional Assumption of a Fixed Past

Observers perceive their history as a sequence of unchangeable events that happened in the past. Considering the standard double slit experiment, the inability to definitely answer “Which slit did the photon choose?” is traditionally resolved by postulating the phenomenon of the wave particle duality, which is independent from other phenomena. Alternatively, the same results would also be observable, if a single fixed past simply did not exist. At first, this idea seems counter-intuitive and raises the question: “If there is no fixed past, what is the past then?”

One possible answer is, that the past could be a superposition of “all allowed quantum states” that “precede” the “now-state” $|t_0\rangle$ in a temporal context. Following this approach, “the past” becomes an unsharp distribution and cannot be defined as a single state. This idea will be revisited later, since in contrast to an “undefined past” the concept of an “undefined future” [7] enjoys notable popularity in Everett's “Many Worlds Interpretation”.

In accordance with the preceding concept, the “nearest past” is the superposition of all quantum states that are compatible (in terms of allowed quantum transitions) with $|t_0\rangle$ and feature a temporal distance of $-t_p$. In non-relativistic approximation, it is possible to define temporal operators P_n and a metric M_t , measuring the temporal distance between $|t_0\rangle$ and one of its “past-states” $P_n(|t_0\rangle)$ in units of t_p . The “nearest past” is described by the operator P_1 ($M_t = -1$),

the “second nearest past” is described by the operator P_2 ($M_t = -2$) and so on. P_2 thus is the “nearest past” of the “nearest past” and therefore a superposition of all “nearest pasts”, which themselves are superpositions. For clarification, all summands are explicitly written out here:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\text{“now-state”} & P_0(|t_0\rangle) = |t_0\rangle \\
\text{“nearest past”} & P_1(|t_0\rangle) = \sum_{i=1}^n |p_i\rangle \\
\text{“second nearest past”} & \text{with } P_1(|p_k\rangle) = \sum_{i=1}^{m_k} |p_{k,i}\rangle \ (1 \leq k \leq n) \\
& P_2(|t_0\rangle) \text{ consists of } \sum_{i=1}^n m_i \text{ summands:} \\
& P_2(|t_0\rangle) = P_1(\sum_{i=1}^n |p_i\rangle) = P_1(|p_1\rangle) + P_1(|p_2\rangle) + \dots + P_1(|p_n\rangle) = \\
& P_1(|p_{1,1}\rangle) + \dots + P_1(|p_{1,m_1}\rangle) + \\
& P_1(|p_{2,1}\rangle) + \dots + P_2(|p_{2,m_2}\rangle) + \dots + P_1(|p_{n,1}\rangle) + \dots + P_1(|p_{n,m_n}\rangle)
\end{array}$$

The nearest past $P_1(|t_0\rangle)$ only depends on $|t_0\rangle$, but $P_1(|p_1\rangle)$ and $P_1(|p_2\rangle)$ are distinct superpositions. Hence the quantum states contributing to the “nearest past” will have separate own and mutually incompatible “nearest pasts”.

3.2 Traditional Assumption of an Open Future

Analogous to the notion of the past, the future is perceived as a sequence of events. Observers consider to have influence on upcoming events. Once they occur, they are supposed to build a new basis for a future influenced by them. This way of thinking directly lead to the Copenhagen Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics.

The transition $-t_p \rightarrow t_p$ defines the future states $F_n(|t_0\rangle)$ ($M_t = n$). The “nearest future” $F_1(|t_0\rangle) = \sum_{i=1}^n |f_i\rangle$ is a superposition of “future-states” and each $|f_i\rangle$ depicts one of the possible multiverses. Each multiverse has its own “nearest future”, represented by $F_1(|f_1\rangle) \neq F_1(|f_2\rangle)$. This corresponds to the everyday observation that upcoming events affect the future succeeding these events. These events cannot be “undone” retroactively. The example in Fig. 1 illustrates the state connections. The splitting factor defines the number of superimposed states of $P_{\pm 1}(|t_0\rangle)$. For illustrative purposes, the exemplary values 2 (P_1) and 5 (P_{-1}) are assumed to be constant within the local proximity of $|t_0\rangle$.

Fig 1: Connection diagram of states when applying permutations of P_1 and P_{-1} (bold) to $|t_0\rangle$. The horizontal distribution of states depicts an arbitrary quantum number to distinguish the states within the same layer of t .

It is noteworthy that though P_n is equivalent to F_{-n} , the “nearest past operator” does not commute with the “nearest future operator” and $[P_n, F_n] \neq 0$. Since $P_1(F_1(|t_0\rangle)) = P_1(P_{-1}(|t_0\rangle)) \neq |t_0\rangle$, the “nearest past” of the “nearest future” is not equal to the “now-state”. The “now-state” rather is a single constituent in the superposition of the “nearest past of the nearest future”. This works in both directions of time, so the “now-state” also does not equal the “nearest future of the nearest past” (see Fig. 1). Since “the past” and “the future” are relative to $|t_0\rangle$, there is no “progression of time” in a traditional sense, such as “active hopping” between single states featuring a temporal distance.

Remarkably, the considered number of states in layer t depends on the respective permutation of the operators P_1 and F_1 , as can be seen in Fig. 1 for example at $t=0$. In this context, also the probability density of observables depends on said operator permutation, not on the absolute value of t . From this key insight follows that under the circumstances under consideration, time is not a meaningful parameter to describe the overall quantum mechanical state of the system. This realization might also explain apparent violations of Born’s Rule or normalization inconsistencies [8] when dealing with probabilities of quantum observables at different times in the traditional “Many Worlds Model” of Everett [9].

The network of connected states can be investigated in more detail if the following special conditions are met during a specific period of time T :

1. relativistic effects and loops in the above network (not explicitly shown in Fig. 1 to focus on the main idea) can be neglected during T
2. the splitting factors of P_1 and P_{-1} can be assumed as approximately constant during T

In this case the number $S(|\psi\rangle, t_\psi)$ of states connected to a reference state $|\psi\rangle$ depends both on the reference state itself, as also on the temporal distance t_ψ to $|\psi\rangle$. $S(|\psi\rangle, 0)=1$, since $P_0(|\psi\rangle) = |\psi\rangle$ is a single state. During the regarded time period T , S takes the role of a partition function and therefore might be related to classical entropy. Remarkably, under the considered conditions, S not only increases with increasing time, but also increases with decreasing time, albeit to a much smaller extent. This behavior is depicted in Fig. 2, which shows $S(|t_0\rangle, t)$ exemplarily as a function of time for different splitting factors of $P_{\pm 1}$

Fig. 2: Number of states compatible to the reference state $|t_0\rangle$ (local, non-relativistic approximation). It increases with increasing temporal distance.

However, if S hypothetically is able to attribute some amount to classic entropy and T can be chosen long-lasting enough, some effects (such as dissipation) should be measurable for processes that occurred very long time ago relative to $|t_0\rangle$. Actually, the uniformity of the background radiation might be interpreted as a vague indication for this predicted effect. In the regarded case, the impact of this effect could presumably also be measurable with other cosmic parameters (e.g. by comparing properties in galaxies of different age). This conjecture demands, that the effect is not superimposed by stronger influences. In the model, the direction of time results from the different splitting factors for P_1 and P_{-1} and the observed increase of entropy in time might be derived from the idea that, figuratively speaking, there are more variants of “future states” than “past states” which are connected with the “now state” as simulated in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: “The flower of time”: Simulation of state connectivity for P_k ($|k| \leq 3$) and splitting factors 2 (P_1) and 10 (P_{-1}), normally distributed progression in two sample quantum numbers Q_1 and Q_2 , $S(|t_0\rangle, k t_p)$ is the number of states in each layer. The variance in $Q_{1,2}$ dissipates faster in the future direction. It is conjectured, that under certain conditions, the increase could cause measurable effects for states far in the past.

3.3 Assumption of a Clear Matter Distribution

The preceding sections suggest that the pure “now-state” takes a special position among other temporal mixed states. This result can be transferred analogously to identify an outstanding “here-state” $|s_0\rangle$. To substantiate this approach, a thought experiment is set up:

Some researchers aim to verify, that a particle-antiparticle generation takes place in a vacuum chamber on the moon. The probability of the process to happen is 50%. The supposed start time can only be indicated by a device in their lab on earth, so they are forced to remotely initiate the measurement. Unfortunately, the recombination time of the particle-antiparticle pair is extremely short. Both the generation to be verified and the recombination are located outside of the relativistic light cone defined by their inertial system on earth. Though the researchers instantly remotely initiate the measurement, the transmission speed of the control signal is limited to the speed of light and they are conceptually never able to verify, if the process happened: The final state after recombination is pure vacuum and thus equals the initial state, just as in the case the process never happened.

Above, the “past” or the “future” was described by a superposition of quantum states. This suggests, it could also apply for quantum states at a spatial distance from the “here-state”. In accordance with the temporal metric M_t , also non-relativistic spatial metrics M_x , M_y , M_z are defined, which measure distances in units of the Planck length l_p . The corresponding quantum operators for each spatial direction are

$$X_n, \tilde{X}_n, Y_n, \tilde{Y}_n, Z_n, \tilde{Z}_n, \text{ where } \tilde{X}_n = X_{-n}, \tilde{Y}_n = Y_{-n}, \tilde{Z}_n = Z_{-n}.$$

Since $X_1(\tilde{X}(|s_0\rangle)) \neq |s_0\rangle$, the “nearest left of the nearest right” is not equal to the “here-state”.

3.4 The Uniqueness of “Here and Now”

Combining the insights of the previous considerations, the complete spacetime is only precise (a pure state) in case of the observer’s “here and now” state, defined as $|Y_0\rangle = |t_0, s_0\rangle$. Other parts of spacetime with spatiotemporal distance to $|Y_0\rangle$ have to be considered as superpositions of states. The number of superposed states in proximity of $|Y_0\rangle$ grows rapidly with the distance measured by M_t , M_x , M_y and M_z . It is emphasized, that all previously defined operators act on states in Minkowski space and neglect relativistic effects. Therefore, the model is an approximation in proximity of $|Y_0\rangle$. Despite this simplification, the suggested operators are well suited for illustrating the proposed concepts. The extension of the set presented operators to Lorentz transformations is outside the scope of this paper. Thus, if it is possible to define a completely symmetric quantum field theory on a generalized Hilbert space, the emerging spacetime likely has to be represented as a mixed state with numerous linear combinations of states.

As discussed in chapter 3.2, the presented model of spacetime does not contain any progression of time. Instead, the “observable spacetime” is considered to be an emergent property depending on a pure state $|Y_0\rangle$ and a permutation of operators applied to it. It is an interesting question what effects would occur if a different state than $|Y_0\rangle$ was chosen as the starting point, i.e. a pure “here and now” state featuring a spatiotemporal distance with respect to $|Y_0\rangle$.

In the following, a pure state represented by a single constituent of the mixed past state $|Y_D\rangle$, i.e. one summand of $P_n(|Y_0\rangle)$, will be used as an example. Comparing the m past of $|Y_D\rangle$ with the $n+m$ past of $|Y_0\rangle$ shows that $P_m(|Y_D\rangle) \neq P_{n+m}(|Y_0\rangle)$, since $P_m(|Y_D\rangle)$ is only included in $P_{n+m}(|Y_0\rangle)$. From the perspective of two observers in $|Y_D\rangle$ and $|Y_0\rangle$ this means, that they perceive different “past versions of spacetime”, though $|Y_D\rangle$ actually is part of the past of $|Y_0\rangle$. This holds even true under non-relativistic, macroscopic conditions and shows once again from a different angle that conforming to the presented model of spacetime, time is not a suitable parameter to define states in a generalized Hilbert space of a “Many Worlds System”.

4 Applied Methods

Axioms are the foundation of scientific theories and as such require a particularly critical and constant review. Conceptually, axioms cannot be proven. They can only be supported by the absence of contradictions to previous observations or by predicting measurable and otherwise inexplicable effects. However, axioms can be ultimately falsified by suitable experiments. This work attempts to falsify the proposed hypothetical axiom by first assuming its validity and then refuting it by the contradiction between its logical implications and experimental observations.

This work attempts to falsify [10] the proposed hypothetical axiom in two ways:

1. By postulating its validity to refute it through contradiction of its logical implications.

hypothesis:

axiom is true

seemingly	⇒	Minkowski space is emergent
opposing	⇒	Standard Model is emergent
observations	⇒	Copenhagen Interpretation is not fundamental
can be	⇒	... upcoming and/ or possibly
reinterpreted	⇒	overlooked observations are compatible with the axiom

2. Directly proving its negation: Due to logical reasons “any representation of a fundamental description of reality must have at least one random parameter implied.”

Both approaches have so far not been effective in disproving the axiom. In particular, any unambiguous proof of the invalidity of the existence of “Many Worlds” would also directly falsify it [11][12].

The suggested model of spacetime is not a necessary condition for the validity of the axiom nor vice versa. However, it appears to be a particularly advantageous starting point for completely symmetric theories based on it. Nevertheless, there might be other possibly better suited concepts for an emergent spacetime and an emergent Standard model.

5 Summary

This article presents the hypothetical axiom of “Complete Symmetry”, which overcomes the inconsistent attribution of importance of symmetries in different areas of modern physics. It is

incompatible with the Copenhagen Interpretation of quantum mechanics and requires spacetime and the Standard Model to be emergent. At first glance the axiom seems simply invalid due to common sense. However, it cannot easily be disproved, because all opposing observations considered so far could be reinterpreted instead.

Thought experiments suggest a novel concept of spacetime, where the “here and now” is a pure quantum state $|Y_0\rangle = |t_0, s_0\rangle$, whereas the state of spacetime at temporally or spatially distant points is a superposition of states. In non-relativistic approximation, these mixed states are generated by iteratively applying quantum transitions to $|Y_0\rangle$ on a Planck scale. Remarkably, the corresponding temporal operators P_1 and P_{-1} ($t_0 \rightarrow t_0 \pm t_p$) do not commute. Thus, the “nearest future” of the “nearest past” is not equal to the “now state” and vice versa. This applies analogously to spatial states and so the energy-mass-distribution in spacetime becomes a probabilistic property which is getting less sharp the more distant a state is from $|Y_0\rangle$. In the suggested model, the wave particle duality is not an independent natural phenomenon and time does not progress in a traditional sense, though it has a direction.

6 Discussion

The analyzed list of opposing observations for the axiom could be incomplete and requires further investigation. A detailed mechanism compliant with the axiom for an emergent spacetime [13], an emergent Standard Model, gravity and their mutual interaction remains yet unknown, although the presented concept opens up promising new approaches. The main objective of this work is to encourage further research based upon the suggested novel, unconventional interpretation of physics. Further research will either disprove the axiom or support it. Both cases might open up a new perspective on the physical world view.

7 Declarations

7.1 Funding

The author declares that no financial support was received for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

7.2 Competing interests

The author declares that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

7.3 Data and Code availability

No additional data was used for this article. No additional code is required to reproduce the results of this article.

The MATLAB® code for generating the diagrams can be downloaded from the Open Science Framework: https://osf.io/gn7c3/?view_only=893d9ca92ebc47ce99e6049c7bd26976

7.4 Author contributions

BG: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing, Simulation

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